

BikeNetKit: Developing an open-source bicycle network software suite for urban planners

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Summary

Contemporary bicycle network planning is largely an ad hoc process based on little empirical evidence, sometimes outsourced to for-profit consultancies working with opaque methods. Therefore, to sustainably boost urban cycling, we urgently need user-friendly, open-source planning software. Here, we document our ongoing work turning 10 raw bicycle network algorithms into **BikeNetKit**, an open-source, reproducible, packaged software suite. **BikeNetKit** is targeted at, and developed with the input of, urban planners and policy-makers. Using the example of bicycle network planning, we share our broader reflections on the research-to-policy pipeline with the geospatial community.

KEYWORDS: bicycle networks, open-source, urban planning, sustainable mobility, Python

1 The BikeNetKit project in a nutshell

We are currently undertaking a 1-year software development project in which we aim to close the gap between research results and actual policy. Existing bicycle network planning algorithms, developed over the past 6 years within our research group and with collaborators, are turned into the packaged open-source Python software **BikeNetKit**. The development is public, all code can be found here: <https://github.com/BikeNetKit>.

2 State of the art in bicycle network planning tools

Contemporary urban bicycle network planning is largely an ad hoc process based on little empirical evidence, sometimes assisted by consultancies working with opaque methods. Algorithms can be of great assistance in turning bicycle network planning into a more empirical and systematic process.

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When such algorithms are created open-source, and developed in a user-friendly way, they become particularly effective and reproducible for planners, even allowing for citizen science and use by sustainable mobility advocates. Examples are the Propensity to Cycle Tool (Lovelace et al., 2017) or A/B Street (Carlino et al., 2024). In fact, in the last few years, bicycle infrastructure planning algorithms have become their own scientific field (Diogo Pinto et al., 2026; Gómez and Calvo-Bascones, 2026).

In this vein, we have started a 1-year software development project to close the gap between research and policy, turning 10 existing bicycle network planning algorithms – developed in the last 6 years at our research group – from raw code into packaged open-source Python software. These algorithms, mostly informed by methods from network science, comprise growing bicycle networks from scratch (Szell et al., 2022) or with added data (Folco et al., 2022), linking network components of partially developed networks (Natera Orozco et al., 2020), finding gaps in well developed networks (Vybornova et al., 2022), assessing cycling infrastructure data quality (Vierø et al., 2024), desire line analysis (Breum et al., 2022), widening bicycle lanes (Lonardi et al., 2025), planning a recreational bicycle node network (Vybornova et al., 2025), or connecting low traffic neighborhoods (Larkin et al., 2025).

The policy impact such algorithms can have has been demonstrated (ITF, 2023). They offer different functionalities for various scales or aspects of the planning process, which are often dependent on the level of development of the bicycle network in the target city. For example, the GrowBike (Szell et al., 2022), LinkBike (Natera Orozco et al., 2020) and FixBike (Vybornova et al., 2022) algorithms and their area of use are shown in Figure 1. While being well applicable, open source, and urgently needed, all these algorithms are so far provided only as ad hoc research code. This status implies that they are not user-friendly, which we are in the process of changing.

3 Creating a software suite: development challenges

Creating a software suite that is usable for urban planners without programming experience comes with certain challenges. Some of the algorithms that are included in this project have been implemented several years ago, which means that they need to be overhauled and rewritten because of deprecated functions and packages that were used in the original code. Ideally, all of the algorithms can be packaged into a consistent software suite with the packaging tool `Pixi`, sharing the same designs both in terms of technical decisions and front-end interface. An additional feature that we aim to implement in the software is making it accessible with an API, so it can be integrated into other solutions. We intend to make use of the `pygeoapi` for this, which is an open-source python implementation of the OGC API suite of standards (Kralidis et al., 2025). Our ongoing process of overhauling the code is done openly, therefore help and contributions from the geospatial community are welcome, especially when it comes to the implementation of the `pygeoapi`. The software will be documented adequately, to ensure usability for planners and transparency for potential contributors from the geospatial community.

Besides these technical hurdles, there are other challenges that are typical for any software development project: designing a software that is not only functional and performing on a technical level,

Figure 1: Scope of application of the GrowBike, LinkBike and FixBike algorithms included in this project. GrowBike can be used to grow a bike network completely from scratch, most appropriate for cities without any developed bicycle infrastructure. LinkBike connects components and can be used if a city has developed some bicycle infrastructure, but needs to connect the different parts. FixBike finds missing links in already mostly developed bicycle networks.

but also usable and easy to understand for the intended target user base. In our scenario this is urban planners, so an integral part of the project is to identify what an urban planner needs to support their work, and what can be expected of them. This task has a strong influence on technical decisions made in the project, especially regarding the front-end interface which planners use to interact with the software. We draw on our network of established connections with municipalities and policy makers to gather this information, but will also get in contact with urban planners at conferences. The goal of the project is also to have an easily accessible web platform, on which the algorithms will be visualized so that planners can get an idea of what the software can offer.

4 Increasing impact through an interactive web platform

Finally, it is not enough to provide functioning software, but the benefits of such a software must be well accessible, also to policy makers and the general public. For a few of the past algorithms we have already developed accompanying interactive data visualization platforms, most importantly <https://growbike.net> 2 and <https://fixbike.net>. However, several of the algorithms are missing such visualizations. To develop such visualizations and to embed them via a consistent web experience, we plan to hire a web developer / visualization expert. We expect the outcome of this task to further close the gap between sustainable planning research and policy making.

Figure 2: Existing visualization for GrowBikeNet, accessible at <https://growbike.net>

5 Building community

We are very interested in feedback from the GIS community, specifically in regards to the implementation of research results into user-friendly software. In the same vein we also plan to share the experiences that we have made in this domain thus far, to potentially inspire others to do the same, or hear about what could potentially be done differently. We believe this is a great way to make an impact with research, and a good example of an applied solution for sustainability.

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Biography

Manuel Knepper is a research assistant at the Networks, Data and Society (NERDS) research group at the IT University of Copenhagen. His current work is focused on turning algorithms developed in research into usable software for non-technical users.

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